

History of the Formation of Ancient Medicine in Central Asia

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Abstract: Central Asia is one of the ancient civilizations, it is here that the first cities, scientific centers, academies and madrasas were formed, the first views on the study of nature and medicine were formed, and on this basis, medicine, astronomy, meteorology, geodesy and exact sciences were highly developed. The Avesta, Behustun rock inscriptions, Indian, Chinese, Greco-Roman sources, as well as the medical works of ancient and medieval Eastern scholars and their significance are described in this article.

Keywords: Central Asia, Avesta, Avicenna, Behustun rock inscriptions, medicine, diagnosis, pharmaceutical field, medical laws, Darulshifa, Kitab as-Saydana fit-tib.

Introduction. It is known from history that Central Asia has long been one of the developed centers of various fields of science, including medicine, and it is in the first book of the Avesta ("Vendidat") that information on medicine is given. The information in this book, written almost 24 centuries ago, still amazes scientists today. It contains a set of laws on physical and spiritual purification. In the Avesta, we find ideas that the centers of vision, hearing, smell and taste are located in the brain. The book says that the "center of life" is in the bone marrow. The book also contains very interesting information on human anatomy and physiology [1].

The Avesta states that not only mental depression, but also physical stress can lead to illness. It is emphasized that surgery and mental sedation are the main methods of treatment in treating patients. The book also provides a lot of information about hygiene, prevention, neatness, avoiding bad things, walking in the fresh air, eating quality food, and drinking clean drinking water. It is in the Avesta that scientific views on medicine and psychology were reflected almost 150 years before Hippocrates.

Based on medical sources in the Avesta, Hippocrates, in his views on the relationship between the brain and the soul, studied human behavior in relation to the course of the disease and created teachings about temperament. Hippocrates divided human temperament into 4 types:

- 1) sanguine - an active, cheerful, strong-willed person;
- 2) choleric - a hot-tempered, emotional person, in whom liver fire predominates;
- 3) phlegmatic - a restrained person, in whose body phlegm (mucus, phlegm) predominates;
- 4) melancholic - a person who is weak-willed, depressed and in a state of anxiety.

Plato expressed his views on the soul in the human body, while Aristotle expressed several of his thoughts on the relationship between the brain, soul, and body. Aristotle divided the soul into three types: plant, animal, and conscious.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE AND METHODS

At the beginning of the 9th century, medicine, along with other natural sciences, was developing rapidly in the East, namely in Baghdad, Bukhara and Khorezm. In the medical institutions of Baghdad, methods of psychological influence were widely used in the treatment of patients. Knowledge began to develop about the relationship between the patient and the medical worker, psychological methods, the importance of psychological factors in the origin of various diseases, their prevention. It would not be an exaggeration to say that during this period the foundations of medical psychology began to be laid. Medical institutions in Baghdad were recognized all over the world and gained great fame in Europe.

The transformation of Central Asia into a center of trade, science, and culture during the ancient Silk Road period gave impetus to the development of the medical field. The ancient peoples of Central Asia used plants, minerals, and animal products as medicines. Later, starting from the 1st century AD, a scientific approach began to strengthen in Central Asian medicine. Under the influence of Greek, Indian, and Chinese medical schools, the causes, diagnosis, and treatment methods of diseases were studied in more depth.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

As a result of these studies, medicine began to flourish in Central Asia, and the largest number of medical works are attributed to this region. In the Middle Ages, the science of medicine began to develop in the East, not only in Central Asia. In particular, the scientific heritage of the great physicians of Central Asia in the 9th-11th centuries - Aby Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Bakr ar-Razi, Abu Rayhan Beruni and other scientists - had a great influence on the development of Eastern and Western medicine. In particular, the work of scientists such as Abu Hasan al-Bayhaki, Ibn al-Kifti, Ibn Abu Usaybia, Abu Bakr ibn al-Khalikan, Abu Bakr ar-Razi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Sharafiddin Iloki, Najmiddin Samarkandi, Ismail Jurjani and other famous physicians played a significant role in the work of such scientists as Abu Bakr ar-Razi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Sharafiddin Iloki, Najmiddin Samarkandi, Ismail Jurjani and other famous physicians[2]. Therefore, Ibn Sina is called the founder of medical science in Central Asia [3].

The greatest merit of the scientist is that he summarized the results achieved by the medicine of that time, enriched it with his own experiences and created scientific research on this basis. He created his 5-volume work "The Canons of Medicine", the first volume of which is about the theory of medical sciences; anatomy, diagnostics, physiology and surgery. The second volume tells about simple medicines. The third and fourth volumes describe diseases of human organs, and the fifth volume talks about complex medicines. [4].

Speaking about the medicine of that time, it is worth mentioning Abu Rayhan Beruni. Abu Rayhan Beruni is a great scholar of Khorezm, the author of famous works on history, medicine, pharmacology, and mineralogy. American historian and scientist J. Sarton describes Beruni as follows; "Astronomy and mathematics, medicine and pharmacology, anthropology and ethnography, philosophy, botany and mineralogy would be impoverished without his great name." The greatest contribution to medicine was that Abu Rayhan Beruni deeply studied medicinal plants and, summarizing his knowledge and observations in this field, created a work called "Kitab as-Saydana fit-tib" (Book of Pharmacognosy of Medicine). In the book, the author clearly showed and defined the properties of more than 1,000 medicinal substances, as well as the methods of their collection and use.[5]

Abu Nasr Al-Farabi is a great thinker and encyclopedist who played an important role in the development of ancient medicine in Central Asia. Although he did not practice medicine directly, he had a great influence on the development of medicine through philosophy, logic, natural sciences and music. In this sense, his treatise "On the Organs of the Human Body" is of great importance. This work confirms that he was a direct predecessor of Abu Ali ibn Sina, the author of the famous "Canon of Medicine", in determining the goals and objectives of medical science. Al-Farabi paid special attention here to the interaction of the organism with the external

environment, the dependence of the mental and physical state of a person on external factors, and the influence of the environment.

Conclusion: Central Asia has been a crossroads of different cultures and civilizations since ancient times. The development of medicine in this region is also associated with these cultural exchanges. In addition, the unique contribution of world-renowned scientists and scholars to the field of medicine has left an indelible mark on the history of Central Asia. Thanks to the scientific heritage accumulated through the scientific and practical experiences of ancient scholars in Central Asia, modern medicine is achieving great success.

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